

The Importance of Social and Humanitarian Sciences In Mature Specialist Training

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Abstract: This article discussed the importance of Social Humanities in the development and application of spiritual and moral qualities in the lives of young people, the role that Social Humanities play in producing a harmonious generation of mature specialists, and the idea that Social Humanities is the force that can awaken the people and the country.

Keywords: socio-humanitarian sciences, professional education, continuing education, social role of education, strategy of humanitarization of education, and upbringing.

One of the most widespread spheres of human endeavor in the contemporary world is education. In most of the world's nations, attitudes toward education in general have altered and education's social significance has grown in recent years. One of the primary driving forces behind social and economic progress is thought to be education. The focus on this topic stems from the fact that the most valuable asset and critical component of contemporary society is an individual with the capacity to seek out, learn, and use new information. Thus, in the modern day, education is crucial to the formation of both the individual and the community. The development of a spiritually and physically harmonious generation and the education of modern, mature personnel are necessary in the current climate of increasing globalization and fierce competition in the global economy. Continuous education throughout an individual's life is preferable to education that was provided for them during their entire childhood. There is a saying among our people that says, "Education and upbringing begin at the cradle." The only path to maturity and the advancement of civilization is enlightenment. It is therefore not in vain that public policy concerning education in our nation seeks to establish a comprehensive and ongoing system founded on the idea of the system of continuing education, which will assist the child in every manner from birth until the age of thirty and aid him in locating a deserving place in life. Given that the advancement of science and the new century are closely linked, it is clear that each sector needs young, competent experts in their respective fields given the rise in demand for staff brought about by scientific advancement. The Republic of Uzbekistan's law "on education" No. 639 of September 23, 2020, and the president's decree "on the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" No. PF-60 of January 28, 2022, were both passed with the intention of guaranteeing the completion of these assigned tasks. The aforementioned law and decree suggest that addressing personnel issues and providing solutions across many businesses is a critical and pressing duty in the modern era. Numerous scientific and practical

works will be required in the educational system in order to address the personnel issue, the labor market, the education system, the identification of the link between producers, and the ongoing execution of integration between them. The creation of a fully harmonious citizenry through a system of continuous education is implied by state policy in the area of personnel training. This process is closely tied to an individual's intellectual, spiritual, and moral education. In this way, one of a citizen's most fundamental constitutional rights—the right to knowledge acquisition, the ability to express creativity, intellectual growth, and the freedom to work—is realized. The impetus behind global progress, which includes Uzbekistan's development, is the presence of skilled, capable professionals who can fulfill the demands of the modern world. The higher education system will surely prepare such persons. As a result, the foundation of development—science, education, and upbringing—gets particular attention from all over the world since it has the potential to make a nation powerful and great. Socio-humanitarian sciences have an unparalleled role in the development of mature specialists. Additionally, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev pointed out that he addressed youth and human resources training in almost every speech he gave, and that in the work "strategy of New Uzbekistan," they gave particular attention to the issue of deepening the teaching of social and humanitarian sciences. At the meeting led by President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on January 19, 2021, Our chief of state gave special attention to this point, emphasizing how crucial socio-humanitarian sciences are to our youth's upbringing. To what extent do the socio-humanitarian sciences play a role in personnel training? In the current circumstances, we greatly value a new generation of young people who have a clear civic viewpoint, defend the interests of the state and society, actively participate in changes and reforms in people's lives, and are modern and open-minded. If we don't develop such people, our youth will grow up in an independent manner. The irrational generation turns into a manger, if not spiritually. In this regard, the president's demand and recommendation may be adequate justification for instituting social science education in postsecondary educational institutions, provided that the socio-humanities are supplemented with new material and the social sciences are taught with serious revision. Ultimately, unlike other technical and economic, commercial, financial, and economic domains, the social sphere does not directly generate substantial cash. However, reality itself is demonstrating that the repercussions and catastrophes brought on by society's spiritual emptiness can result in irreversible tragedies. Regretfully, some of our fellow citizens are also in favor of this kind of movement. The emergence of religious currents based on the consequences of religious fanaticism—global terrorism, ignorant animosity, the urchination of the ideas of Savodi Haminqadar Chalamullas and their suspects abroad, which correspond to neither religion nor human spirituality—to the horror of an individual—was seen as a threat to the world as a result of a gap in the socio-humanities. Mature professionals can be trained with less socio-humanitarian disciplines.

Raising a true patriot—someone who feels sorrow for the country—is a far more challenging endeavor. The socio-humanitarian sciences are necessary if we are to help young people understand the fundamentals of the third Renaissance, no matter how much we talk about it or strive to. The "catalyst" for the start and progression of the third Renaissance is found in the socio-humanities. The socio-humanitarian sciences are thought to be a force that can awaken the populace and the country. Accordingly, between 2022 and 2030, Developing and putting into action a plan to humanize the Republic of Uzbekistan's continuing education and education system is advised. Then and only then will we be able to train contemporary employees who are well-versed in every field.

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